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Determining The Types Of Test Formats And Assessment Scoring Procedures Used By Teachers In Business Studies In Gashua Educational Zone, Yobe State.

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the types of test formats and assessment scoring procedures used by Teachers in Business studies in Gashua Educational Zone Yobe State. The objectives of the study was to determine the types of test formats in Business studies teachers use in teacher-made tests and to examine the processes how Business Studies teachers follow in assessing their students. The study used descriptive survey design. The population of this study consisted of (465) participants from (18) junior secondary schools that offer business studies were (415) students and (50) teachers were selected through simple random sampling techniques. The instrument used for the study was checklist to collect the data. The data collected were analyzed using frequency, percentage and counts. The study revealed that, most of the teachers used conventional multiple choice with 52.3% than any other type of tests format, it also revealed that most teachers do not follow the procedure for assessment and scoring. Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made: Principals of Junior Secondary Schools should encourage teachers to use various types of tests format in their assessments and there is need for Yobe state Universal Basic Education to organize workshop and training for their teachers.

Keywords: Secondary School, Teacher-Made Test and Business Studies.

INTRODUCTION

Assessment is fundamental to the educational process because it provides systematic evidence of student achievement and informs instructional decision-making. Among the many decisions teachers make, the selection of an appropriate test format is particularly consequential. Test formats influence not only what knowledge and skills are measured but also how students engage with learning tasks. Different formats capture different cognitive processes, from recall and recognition to analysis, synthesis, and application. Consequently, teachers must understand the characteristics, benefits, and limitations of various test formats to design assessments that accurately reflect instructional goals.

Teacher-made tests bring assessment and teaching together for the benefit of the students and provide the teacher with opportunity to participate in a unique way in the assessment process that leads to the final grade obtained by his or her students. The primary purpose of teacher-made test is to enhance the validity

of the assessment by including assessment of outcomes that cannot be readily assessed within the context of a single public examination. As Mpofu (2011) states, for a teacher to be able to do his/her work effectively, he/she needs to assess the progress of his or her pupils from time to time. Similarly, a good knowledge of where the pupil is and how he/she is progressing helps the teacher to effectively cater for the needs of pupils (Chakanyika, 2000). Also, Anastasi and Urbina (2008) noted that the impact of community programs and influence of environmental variables on human performance rely on tests for good outcome. The many kinds of tests designed for these purposes differ in their major characteristics. They vary in the way they are administered as individual testing of each person by a trained examiner like teachers in the case of teacher –made tests, the simultaneous testing of large group in the school environments.

Regarding Business studies, teacher-made tests are tests designed to assess the degree of mastering of specific unit of instruction taught by the teacher. They are tailored to measure the achievement of students and intended objectives for them after completing a series of learning tasks for the course. Sithole (2010) opined that the effectiveness of teacher-made tests in Business studies therefore, depends on its quality because it provides relevant measures of many important learning outcomes and indirect evidence concerning test. Furthermore, Adetayo (2008) maintain that Teacher- made tests also have positive impact on teaching and learning; helping to motivate students by engaging them into meaningful activities, reinforcing curriculum aims and good teaching practice among teachers, providing structure and significance for daily teaching activities, namely, for teachers to assess their own students. Also, Atakpa (2011) stress that the validity and reliability of the information provide however, depends on the care that goes in to planning preparation of the test

Teacher-made tests play a very significant role in that they are part of the teaching and learning process. Madziyire (2010) hypothesizes that, teacher-made tests help the teacher to identify the content (knowledge or skills) which has been mastered by pupils and the teacher to understand the results from his/her tests, the areas where the pupils have difficulties and then find ways of overcoming the difficulties so that the pupils can do better. Ogunniyi (2004) observed that, teacher-made tests give a more immediate measure of progress and achievement of learners; guides and improves instruction, diagnoses learners' knowledge of a topic. Teacher-made tests provide feedback so that teachers can shift the emphasis of their instruction and provide remedial activities before the next lesson (Kolawale, 2010). Furthermore, James & Pedder (2006) suggested that, teacher-made tests are used as continuous assessment tool which provides more information that is more reliable than examinations or standardized tests. Therefore, well-constructed teacher-made tests give students the opportunity of assessing their knowledge immediately and constructive feedback which will help the learners to improve their performance (Sax, 2007).

Educational programmes are established for specific purposes. Programme evaluation in education, according to Nworgu (2003) is indispensable, as evaluation serves to provide an objective basis for effecting necessary modifications and evolving strategies for improving performance. Commenting on the importance of evaluation, Cangelosi(2009), asserts that 'one important reason for evaluation of Teacher-made tests amongst others is to diagnose student's weaknesses with a view to improving future performance'. Also to identify the need for teachers to be helped in order to understand the important roles which properly constructed, administered and scored tests play in preparing students for external examinations.

The criteria for evaluating teacher-made tests is the degree of conformity of teacher-made tests to technical guidelines for test construction; the learning outcome measured; the Procedure for preparing Teacher-Made Tests, the degree of content validity, score reliability and predictive validity. The test tools are supposed to reflect behavioral change expected of the student's after an instruction. For a teacher to construct valid and reliable instruments for classroom assessment, he or she must adhere to item writing instructions, procedures of assessment, reflect topics available in the national objectives. Haladyna, Downing & Rodriguez (2002) support the view that effective use of teacher-made tests require the assessment of their quality in terms of conformity to technical guidelines for test construction, learning outcomes they measure, their validity and reliability and in their submissions observed that perceived

overreliance on the multiple choice format to measure the recall of knowledge instead of higher level of learning has resulted in disenchantment with multiple-choice testing. They reported two sources of evidence in their study as strategies for the collective opinions of textbooks authors and second source was empirical research which they made a collective judgment about the validity of each guideline after considering both sources of evidence and produced thirty one items-writing guidelines. Each of thirty one item-writing guidelines was subjected to the same validation procedure. This was to ensure that multiple-choice test items developed by test constructors in conformity to the multiple-choice item writing guidelines can be said to be of quality.

Audu (2014) confirmed that, the processes involved are identification and definition of objective by the teacher, choosing and developing appropriate instruments for measuring the objectives; administration of test to the group of students; scoring the responses of each students (represent their performance); decisions are made on the basis of the scores of each individual students and report the performance to the relevant bodies. Another study conducted by Atsua (2012) on predictive validity of teacher-made tests in relation to WAEC and NECO SSCE economics for three years from year 2009/2010, 2010/2011 and 2011/2012 academic sessions and used five senior secondary schools in Maiduguri Metropolis. The study sampled off two thousand nine hundred and fifty one (2,951) SSIII students for the study. The result of the study indicated a substantial significant correlation relationship between teacher-made tests and WAEC SSCE economics at $p < 0.05$ level of significance.

The adequacy of the act of teaching must be judged in terms of the degree of which the students fall short of their potentials, the onus must be borne by the teacher and other responsible agents who constitute the educational environment. The present poor performance in business studies have not been encouraging but rather disheartening in the study area. This may be as a result of the quality of teacher-made test. In relation to these, there had been public criticism and disappointment over the student's performances in business studies BECE examinations in Yobe State. This situation has not changed creditably as Atakpa (2011) also expressed the same view, attributing these failures to bad teaching.

Statement of the Problem

The adequacy of the act of teaching must be judged in terms of the degree of which the students fall short of their potentials, the onus must be borne by the teacher and other responsible agents who constitute the educational environment. The present poor performance in business studies have not been encouraging but rather disheartening in the study area. This may be as a result of the quality of teacher-made test. In relation to these, there had been public criticism and disappointment over the student's performances in business studies BECE examinations in Yobe State. This situation has not changed creditably as Atakpa (2011) also expressed the same view, attributing these failures to bad teaching. It is against this background that, the researcher was to determine the types of Test formats and Assessment Scoring Procedures used by Teachers in Business Studies in Gashua Educational Zone, Yobe State.

Objectives of the Study

The following objectives were used for the study to;

- a. determine the types of test formats Business studies teachers use in teacher-made tests
- b. examine the processes, how Business Studies teachers follow in assessing their students

Research Questions

- a. What are the types of test formats, Business studies teachers use in teacher-made tests?
- b. What processes do Business Studies teachers follow in assessing their students?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Types of Test formats in Teacher-Made Tests

Test formats are the various types of test classroom teacher's use in assessing their students in schools. The test formats used in assessing students include: Selected-response tests such as (Multiple choice, matching, true/false), Selected-response tests e.g (short answer and essay questions). Performance-based assessments such as observation, conferences, portfolios, administering of test, scoring of test, peer and group assessments techniques have equally been used and Digital and Technology-Enhanced Test

Formats this include computer-adaptive testing, interactive simulations, and multimedia-based tasks. The preparation of each of these assessments is important in ensuring the validity of the information generated (Afemikhe & Imobekhai 2014 and Popham, 2017).

Obioma (2011), conducted study on teacher-made tests practices in primary and Junior Secondary Schools in Nigeria. A large scale survey was conducted on a sample of 3,325 teachers across six geo-political zones of the country. Data were analyzed using percentage. Results emanated from the study revealed conventional multiple choice, 17.5% of the teachers used matching test item frequently, 33.5% used true/false; yes/no frequently. Similarly, these formats are widely used because they allow efficient administration and objective scoring. In large classrooms or standardized testing environments, selected-response items provide a practical means of assessing broad content coverage within limited time constraints. By and large, the Technology-enhanced assessments also support innovative item types, such as drag-and-drop classification, virtual laboratories, and scenario-based problem solving. These formats can measure complex skills while maintaining efficient scoring procedures. However, access to technology and digital literacy disparities raise concerns about equity and fairness. (DeLuca et al., 2016; Xu & Brown, 2016; Pastore, 2023; Lei & Lei, 2026)

Hamman-Tukur and Audu (2015), undertook an assessment of procedure and quality of teachers' assessment in agricultural science in senior secondary schools in Borno State. The study used survey design, a random sample of 265 agricultural science teachers out of a population of 315 participated in the study; checklist and proforma was developed and used to collect data for the study. Data were analysed using percentage and Pearson Product Moment Correlation. The result shows that 88.7% of the teachers used restricted essay, 88.1% used conventional multiple choice and continuous assessment was administered two to three times in a term. The study was in line with Tofighi and Ahmadi Safa (2023) in their study, Fairness in Language Classroom Assessment Practices that, Analyses of the data gathered from 120 EFL teachers indicated that fairness principles of equal chances to learn, unambiguity, the chance to indicate learning, do-no-harm principle, and score pollution avoidance in its definition of test fairness.

Aduloju and Moses (2016), studied assessment of secondary school teacher-made tests in Benue State, the design adopted for the study was survey. The population for the study was four hundred and twenty six (426) teachers of economics in senior secondary school Benue State. Sample 295 teachers were selected based on proportional stratified random sampling. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistic. Results showed that seventy (70) percent of the respondents frequently used multiple choice questions; ninety (90) percent frequently used essay test questions. The findings above indicated that, most of the teachers used multiple choice questions and essay test questions. Constructed-response tasks allow teachers to evaluate depth of understanding, reasoning processes, and communication skills. They are particularly valuable in disciplines that emphasize explanation, interpretation, and argumentation. (Akayuure, 2021; Armah, 2025; Asamoah et al., 2023). The findings also found that, Performance assessments provide rich evidence of student competence because they integrate cognitive, procedural, and sometimes collaborative skills. They are particularly effective for evaluating problem-solving, creativity, and application of knowledge across contexts. From the foregoing, it can be seen that one of the standards for teachers' assessment competencies is their capacity to design and create tests. This standard indicates the test construction skills they need to have (Kissi, 2020).

Processes for developing of Teacher-Made Tests

Certain sequential steps are identifiable in the conduct of test and examinations. The processes involved are identification and definition of objective by the teacher, choosing and developing appropriate instruments for measuring the objectives; administration of test to the group of students; scoring the responses of each students (represent their achievement); decisions are made on the basis of the scores of each individual students and report the achievement to the relevant bodies. (Audu 2014)

Setlthomo (2012), surveyed Botswana primary and secondary school teacher's classroom assessment practices, 1000 teachers were randomly sampled from the teachers' population of 6000 in primary and secondary schools. Four research questions were raised for the study. Data were collected using

questionnaires and were analyzed using chi-square at 0.05 and sample percentage. The major findings of the study indicated that fifteen percent of the teachers planned evaluation based on topic taught, 35% informed students in advance about tests, 12% of teachers supervised students during tests to ensure students do not cheat during test or examinations; most of the teachers use marking scheme during scoring, 13% interpreted student's achievement and 93% reported the result of student's achievement to parents and educationists.

Wale (2013), carried out a study on teachers' quality and internal efficiency in secondary school in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The study used the quantitative paradigm and adopted the descriptive survey design. The population comprised of all secondary schools in Ekiti State. The sample consisted of 120 teachers from 30 schools randomly selected. Results emanated from the study showed that 98% of the respondents indicated that they were not using table of specification in designing and constructing their continuous assessment test. Also only 15% of the 250 teachers accepted that their items were screened and face-validated by the principals before the tests were administered. The problem of these is that the teachers do not adopt the approved procedure of building tests and content validity into their tests. Test developed without applying such mechanism of quality enhancement are bound to be non-valid in content objectives coverage irrespective of the knowledge and teaching experience. (Akayuure, 2021; Armah, 2025; Asamoah et al., 2023)

Hamman-Tukur and Audu (2015), carried out a study on the assessment for procedures of teacher's assessment in agricultural science in senior secondary schools in Borno State. The result shows that 98.1% of agricultural science teachers do not carry out assessment based on defined instructional objective, did not use table of specification in planning the test and carry out the item analysis. The study concluded that agricultural science teachers in Borno State Senior Secondary School did not follow recommended procedures in testing their students. (Kissi et-al, 2023)

Thembinkosi, Tichaona, and Philip (2015), conducted a study on the effectiveness of teacher-made test on the achievement of pupils in Nkayi District in Matabeleland North in Western Zimbabwe. The study used the quantitative paradigm and adopted the descriptive survey design. The population comprised all the primary schools in Nkayi district. The sample consisted of 120 teachers from 30 schools randomly selected. Each school provided 4 teachers for the study. Of the sampled respondents, 65 were female and 56 male. All the information was collected through a questionnaire which had both close-ended and open-ended questions. Descriptive statistical analysis was used to interpret data. The results of the study indicate that teacher-made test are given to pupils in the schools and there was overwhelming acceptance by the respondents that these tests helped to improve the academic achievement of pupils. It was also found that most teachers did not have knowledge about the standard procedures of constructing, marking, scoring and grading of tests. (Kissi et-al, 2023). The study recommends that there was need for schools to conduct staff development programmes to equip teachers with skills to construct teacher-made tests. The findings above indicated that, most of the teachers do not carry out assessment based on defined instructional objective, did not use table of specification in planning the test and carry out the item analysis. It appears that teachers in Secondary School did not follow recommended procedures in testing their students.

METHODOLOGY

The study used descriptive survey design. The total population for the study was four hundred and sixty five (465). This comprised of four hundred and fifteen (415) students from the sampled schools and Fifty (50) Teachers from the sampled schools. To determine the sample size, a Krejcie and Morgan table (1970) were used to select eighteen (18) schools in Gashua Educational zone. A total number of three hundred and eighty three (383) students in Business studies were obtained from the sampled schools, and fifty (50) Business Studies Teachers were used to evaluate the Procedure

The instrument used for the study was checklist. The data collected were analyzed using frequency and Percentage counts.

RESULTS

Table 1.

Frequency and percentage of Type of Tests Formats used by Business Studies Teachers in Evaluation

S/No.	Type of Teacher-made test	Frequency of usage in (%)
1	Essay Question	110 (28.7%)
2	Fill in the Blank	43 (11.2%)
3	Conventional Multiple Choice	200 (52.3%)
4	True/False	30 (7.8%)
	Total	383 100%

Table 1. results revealed that 52.3% of the teachers used conventional multiple choice, 28.7% of the teachers used essay questions, 11.2% used fill in the Blank and 7.8% used True/False. This showed that most of the teachers used conventional multiple-choice than any other type of tests format

Table 2.

Frequency and percentage of Process Business Studies Teachers used in evaluating their Students in Gashua Educational Zone

S/No	Procedure of Evaluation	Yes	No	Total
1	Determining the purpose of testing	50(100%)	0(0%)	50(100%)
2	Development of evaluation based on clearly defined objectives	3(6%)	47(94%)	50(100%)
3	Developing the test specification/table of specification for planning classroom evaluation	0(0%)	50(100%)	50(100%)
4	Selecting appropriate test items types	6(12%)	44(88%)	50(100%)
5	Preparing relevant test items	5(10%)	45(90%)	50(100%)
6	Assembling the test	2(4%)	48(96%)	50(100%)
7	Administering the test	50(100%)	0(0%)	50(100%)
8	Constructing a model answer for scoring essay questions (marking Scheme)	24(48%)	26(52%)	50(100%)
9	Appraising the test	34(68%)	16(32%)	50(100%)
10	Items analysis (discrimination and difficulty index)	0(0%)	50(50%)	50(100%)
11	Using the result/ report students' progress to parents and educationist	15(30%)	35(70%)	50(100%)

Table 2 showed teachers use various processes of developing tests in Business studies. The results revealed that 94% of the teachers do not developed their evaluation based on clearly defined objectives, 88% of Business study teachers do not select appropriate test item types. Also 96% of the teachers do not assembled the test items base on the topics. The study further revealed that none 0% of the Business study teachers determine the quality of test such as item discrimination and difficulty index. It also revealed that majority of the teachers hardly report student's progress to educational stakeholders, while 30% of Business study teachers prepared model for scoring essay questions.

DISCUSSION

The study showed that most of the teachers used conventional multiple-choice than any other type of tests format. The findings agreed with that of Obioma (2011) who found that most of the teachers used conventional multiple choice than the other types of test format. He further added that the consequences of considering more of conventional multiple choice in examination is that students may not develop their writing skills and vocabulary which are basic skills required for optimum performance while serving the nation in different places of work. Findings from this study provide unique and compelling evidence in the Nigerian context regarding teachers' perceived test construction competence and analysis of teachers-

constructed multiple-choice tests. Examinations results are used to make high stake decisions regarding schools, teachers, and students (Baidoo-Anu and Ennu Baidoo, 2022).

It also showed that teachers use various processes of developing tests in Business studies. The results revealed that 94% of the teachers do not developed their evaluation based on clearly defined objectives, 88% of Business study teachers do not select appropriate test item types. Also 96% of the teachers do not assembled the test items base on the topics. The study further revealed that none 0% of the Business study teachers determine the quality of test such as item discrimination and difficulty index. It also revealed that majority of the teachers hardly report student's progress to educational stakeholders, while 30% of Business study teachers prepared model for scoring essay questions. The study were in line with the findings of Akujieze and Ifeakor (2016) who investigated attitude of teachers towards the construction of test for quality assessment delivery in secondary education in Onitsha education zone Anambra State and found out that item analysis were rarely done by secondary school teachers thereby comprising quality of assessment tests.

CONCLUSION

This study concluded that most of the teachers used multiple choice questions and essay test questions. While least teachers used matching test item, true/false and yes/no and at the same time they do not carry out assessment based on defined instructional objective, they are also not using table of specification in planning the test and carry out the item analysis. It appears that teachers in Secondary School are not following the recommended procedures in testing their students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are made based on the findings of the study

1. Principals of Junior Secondary Schools should encourage teachers to use various types of tests format in their assessments.
2. Based on the discrepancy that exist in teacher-made tests in Gashua education zone and Psychological Testing, teachers should be encourage to cover all the curriculum content which was design by the curriculum developers
3. There is need for Yobe state Universal Basic Education to organize workshop and training for their teachers of business studies in the area of test development so they can improve on their quality of tests.

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